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Perspectives towards hotel stay amidst the COVID-19 pandemic recovery stage: A research from Calamba City, Philippines

Abstract

After the global tourism industry has experienced the impact of the pandemic, it is critical that people gain confidence in traveling and have the impression that staying in hotels is now safe, because only in this way tourism businesses such as hotels can be fully successful in recovering. For this reason, the researchers guided by a descriptive research design and quantitative research approach, aimed to determine what people think about staying in a hotel, particularly in terms of safety and security, price, location, and service quality, in the time of COVID-19 pandemic recovery stage, focused on the local community of Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines, being one of richest cities in the country and the place where the researchers reside. Moreover, a comparative analysis of the perspective of the respondents has been performed in terms of their age, sex, and educational attainment, identifying which age, sex and educational attainment groups have more positive or negative attitude, and a higher or lower level of hotel stay intention compared with other groups. Being the first study that has assessed the tourism market particularly in terms of their perspective on hotel stay as the hospitality industry attempts to recover from the impact of the pandemic, this is expected to provide a clear picture of the need for management of hotels to continuously work on marketing efforts highlighting the information that it is now safe to practice tourism and stay in their establishments, hence, serving as a guide in coming up with promotional strategies and an action plan, as well as a motivation for researchers who wish to determine the same in their locality or country.

Keywords: *Hotel, Hospitality industry, Hotel stay, People's perspective, COVID-19 pandemic recovery*

Jel Codes: Z32, Z31, M30

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1. Introduction

The Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), which first appeared in a seafood and poultry market in the Chinese City of Wuhan in 2019, is an infectious disease that can cause severe respiratory sickness in humans. It is transmitted from person to person through close contact. The cases have been discovered in 214 countries globally, and the World Health Organization declared the outbreak a pandemic on March 11, 2020. The first incidence was documented in the Philippines in January 2020, and since then, the number of coronavirus patients in the country has steadily increased, reaching 3,980,629 as of October 16, 2022. Numerous frightening incidents occurred not just in the Philippines but around the world, due to the drastic spread and the death of many. Many people suffered since it impacted their lives, particularly their general health, lifestyle, the economy, school system, and, most notably, tourism, because travel restrictions were implemented. This pandemic has definitely had a massive impact on the Philippine economy, especially on the sustainability of the tourism industry.

Health emergencies have a reputation to significantly affect business operations, particularly in the hospitality industry that totally relies on the movement of people. The Influenza A (H1N1) has done this in 2009, as well as the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome, which is also known as SARS in 2003, and the COVID-19 that until today continuously gives people fear. The COVID-19 pandemic has clearly had an impact on the tourism and hospitality business, which is entirely dependent on the mobility of people, particularly in countries where tourism is regarded as a vital factor of development, such as the Philippines. UNWTO (2020) has recorded a 10 year sustained growth in international tourist arrivals globally reaching 1.5 Billion in 2019 and a USD 1.7 Trillion in revenue, making tourism as one of the fastest and best sustained industries in the world. However, these have all changed when the pandemic happened; International tourist arrivals globally dropped to 381 Million by the end of 2020 from 1.5 Billion as stated, which is a -74% drop, Asia and the Pacific being the most affected having only 57 Million International Tourist Arrivals from 360 Million the previous year, which is equivalent to -84% decrease.

Krishnan et al. (2020) suggested that the hotel sector is among the most affected in the tourism industry, and that recovery to pre-COVID-19 levels might take until 2023 or beyond. In terms of employee perspectives, the study of Yin et al. (2022) discovered that job insecurity and turnover intention increased among hotel employees during the pandemic due to decreased hotel operating performance; additionally, the larger the hotel where the employees work, the higher their job insecurity and turnover over are. According to Jung et al. (2021), when job insecurity develops, it has a considerable impact on employees' job engagement as well as turnover intention. This is consistent with the findings of Bufquin et al. (2021), who discovered a positive effect of psychological distress caused by the danger of contracting COVID-19 at work on turnover intention during the pandemic. In the Philippines, hotels were utilized as an isolation facility for persons under observation due to the overwhelming number of cases registered day after day, causing overcrowding in hospitals. This has resulted in factors influencing turnover intention that are primarily focused on employees' emotions, such as psychological distress and anxiety, as they may be concerned about providing face-to-face services to regular customers because some COVID-19-infected individuals may be asymptomatic (Betsch, 2020, & Haleem et al. 2020). Croes et al. (2021) reported that in selected states in the United States of America, nearly half of the hotel employees-respondents experienced a reduction in work time, and more than one-third of

employees revealed that they did not have enough money to meet monthly expenses as a result, while nearly two of five respondents voiced concerns for their health and safety due to COVID-19, and approximately 10% have already decided to switch jobs before the conduct of the study, which indicate that an overwhelming majority of hospitality employees experienced one or more of the following; job loss, business closure, and reduction of hours and pay. In the same study, it was found out that one-third of unemployed respondents have either left the industry with no intention of returning or are considering leaving to pursue other professional opportunities in other industries, while some employees expressed that they are hesitant to return to the industry due to the risks of COVID-19 exposure, indicating that the COVID-19 pandemic has influenced employees' perspective towards the hospitality industry. Hervie et al. (2022) discovered the same in Ghana, revealing that 80% of the 511 employees of 58 hotels in the Greater Accra Region had their incomes decreased, and that work schedules and working hours were adjusted, notably during the country's lockdown and closing of its borders.

Government policies such as lockdowns, social distancing, and travel and movement limitations, among others, have resulted in the temporary closure of numerous hospitality enterprises and severely reduced demand for those that were allowed to continue operating (Bartik et al., 2020). According to the American Hotel and Lodging Association's 2021 report, hotels in the United States lost nearly USD 83.7 billion in room revenue in 2020, compared to what the sector has earned in 2019, and job losses were nearly 630,000, which is nearly half of hotel markets, accounting for 72% of hotels in the US expressing to be in a depression stage. Negative effects on the hospitality businesses were also observed in China, as Hao et al. (2020) highlighted, with the nation seeing a dramatic fall in hotel occupancy rates and a revenue loss of more than USD 9 billion. According to the report, around 74% of hotels in China were closed for an average of 27 days in January and February 2020, and occupancy rates decreased from roughly 70% during the pandemic, resulting in a fall in the number of staff and a considerable loss in cash flow and income. In the Philippines, based on the findings of Pew Research Center (2020), 33% of tourism related businesses including hotels have seen 33% productivity loss due to the employees' lack of remote work capabilities, 29% change in staffing due to low demand, and 27% layoffs.

Two years later, governments, particularly the Philippine government, begin to reopen their economies by lifting travel bans and allowing businesses to reopen, alongside a significant increase in the number of vaccinated people and the implementation of policies that remove the requirement of wearing face masks and shields in public places, indicating that the country is in the process of recovering from the pandemic. The UNWTO created the Tourism Recovery Tracking System to cover worldwide international tourist arrivals, seat capacity in international and domestic air routes, air travel bookings, hotel searches and bookings, occupancy rates and demand for short term rentals, and travel sentiments; in the case of South East Asia, this attempt to recover can be seen in the improvement on the international tourist arrivals, which is -65% as of July 2022 compared to what has been recorded in 2019, which is from -96% in January 2022, while in terms of Occupancy Rate, 57% has been recorded in August 2022 compared to 43% in January 2022.

Obviously, the tourism industry, most especially the hotel sector is already trying to make a comeback and little by little recover from the negative effects the pandemic has brought to its operations, but as this happens, it is also important that people would gain the confidence of travelling and have that impression that staying in hotels is now safe, because through this way only hotels can be fully successful, most especially that data shows occupancy rate has decreased once again in August 2022 after continuous increase in the 1st and 2nd quarter of the year, particularly in South East Asia. For these reasons, the researchers have decided to conduct this study that aims to determine what people thinks about the industry during the recovery stage, leading to a conclusion of whether people were able to understand the real situation in the hospitality industry or has it remained in their minds that staying in hotels is

still not a good idea due to the threat of COVID-19. This study as a result of rigorous search in open access journals, has been determined to be the first to assess the tourism market particularly in terms of its perspective on hotel stay as the hospitality industry attempts to recover from the impact of the pandemic, which could provide a clear picture of the need to continuously work on marketing efforts highlighting the fact that it is now safe to practice tourism, and is expected to serve as a guide and motivation for researchers who wish to learn if the same situation occurs in their locality or country. The researchers have attempted to accomplish the following specific research objectives:

1. To determine what the local community of Calamba City, Philippines thinks about staying in a hotel, particularly in terms of safety and security, price, location, and service quality, in the time of COVID-19 pandemic recovery stage.
2. To determine what age, sex and educational attainment groups have more positive or negative perspective towards hotel stay, and a higher or lower level of hotel stay intention compared with other groups.

2. Literature Review

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a negative impact on tourists' traveling behavior, resulting in a significant decrease in the number of travelers. In fact, in the study of Hotle et al. (2020), people are more interested in staying at home than traveling because they are afraid of becoming infected by the virus while enjoying leisure. As a result, it discourages individuals from going, particularly to high-risk locations. This is consistent with the findings of Gursay et al. (2020), who found that more than 50% of people are unwilling to eat at a restaurant during the pandemic, and they also reject the thought of traveling to a place and staying at a hotel any time soon. In the same study, only around 25% of all survey respondents had dined in a restaurant, and only one-third plan to go to a place and stay in a hotel in the next several months. Several studies have been conducted during the pandemic to investigate the impact of the pandemic on visitor perceptions; Hassan and Soliman (2021) said that perceived trust and reputation of the place is one of them. In addition, destination social responsibility and previous experience (Hu and Xu, 2021), perceived risk (Wang et al. 2020), perceived probability of infection (Golets et al., 2020), travel anxiety, and fear of COVID-19 (Luo and Lam, 2020) were also found to have an impact on people's interest toward travel and visiting places. Meanwhile, according to Mirzaei et al. (2021), due to the situation, health and safety have risen to the top of passengers' priorities; hygiene and disinfection of tourism facilities have shifted from hygiene to motivational elements. The aviation sector has also suffered as a result of the pandemic; however, it is not just travel restrictions enforced by most governments throughout the world that have resulted in lower passenger numbers, but also changes in travel behavior induced by the COVID-19 pandemic itself (Neuburger and Egger, 2020). According to Abdullah et al. (2020), travelers fear becoming infected with COVID-19 while traveling outside of their country, with the level of risk varying depending on the end destination and its current COVID-19 situation, which has resulted in many passengers delaying or canceling their flights. All these data clearly indicate that attitude has a significant impact on people's travel intentions. According to Seong and Hong (2021), if a person has a favorable attitude toward a location, he or she is more likely to visit, but if one has a negative attitude about a place, he or she is unlikely to come, no matter how appealing it is in reality.

Aside from these findings, data shows that the pandemic has negatively affected the tourism industry; one of the many is the drastic downturn on tourist arrivals worldwide as presented in table 1.

Table 1: Data on International Tourist Arrivals in 2019 versus 2020 worldwide by region.

Region	2019 International Tourist Arrivals	2020 International Tourist Arrivals	Percentage Drop
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Americas	219 Million	69 Million	-69%
Europe	749 Million	221 Million	-70%
Africa	70 Million	18 Million	-75%
Middle East	65 Million	16 Million	-75%
Asia and The Pacific	360 Million	57 Million	-84%

Source: United Nations World Tourism Organization.

More than two years later, with the effectiveness of policies implemented during the peak of the pandemic and the compliance of people on vaccination, the world begins to see a recovery phase. In fact, data shows increased tourist arrivals as well as hotel occupancy rates, specifically in Asia and the Pacific, with the exception of some regions as presented in figure 1 and 2.

Figure 1: International Tourist Arrivals Percentage in 2022 VS 2019 in Asia and the Pacific. Source: United Nations World Tourism Organization.

Figure 2: Hotel Occupancy Rates in 2022 VS 2019 in Asia and the Pacific. Source: United Nations World Tourism Organization.

Indeed, there are several studies that have explored COVID-19 pandemic and the tourism industry, however, these have focused on limited topics only such as influence of the pandemic on people’s travel behavior, factors that has affected tourists’ perception, and the

impact of the pandemic on business profitability and sustainability. Two years later, no researcher has studied people's perspective towards traveling and staying in hotels in this time when economies and businesses are already recovering from the pandemic, particularly in the Philippines, which could serve as an indicator whether hospitality businesses can easily bounce back or will have to wait until people's confidence in tourism regains. Hence, a research gap that this study have attempted to fill.

3. Methodology

Following a descriptive research design and utilizing a quantitative research approach, the researchers were able to gather, analyze, and interpret data for this study. Through number scales, data were measured and interpreted, while statistical formulas were used to determine significant differences. Out of the total population of Calamba City, Laguna, which is 539,671 based on the 2020 Census of the Philippines Statistics Authority, the sample size was computed with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level, resulting to 384 needed respondents for this research, who were selected randomly. People to qualify as respondents must be residing in Calamba City, Laguna, at least 18 years old during the conduct of this study, employed or a business owner with regular income, and have stayed at least once in a hotel in the last 5 years.

The research instrument used was created based on the studies of Tuan (2019) and Soulidou et al. (2018), where the factors that influence people's decision to stay in a hotel were taken from. It is a survey composed of 23 questions, 3 of which were asked to determine the respondents' demographic profile, and 20 were designed to learn about their perspectives towards hotel stay in terms of safety and security, location, price, and service quality. To measure the people's perspective, a four-point scale was used whereas; 1-Strongly Agree, 2-Agree, 3-Disagree, and 4-Strongly Disagree. It was made using Google Docs, distributed through direct messaging in a social media platform, which has recorded a 100% response rate from all people that have been asked (see table 2).

Table 2: Likert Scale Interpretations on respondents' perspective on hotel stay and their intention.

Survey Responses	Perspective Interpretation	Hotel Stay Intention Interpretation	Scale
Strongly Disagree	Very Positive	Very High Stay Intention	3.26-4.00
Disagree	Positive	High Stay Intention	2.51-3.25
Agree	Negative	Low Stay Intention	1.76-2.50
Strongly Agree	Very Negative	Very Low Stay Intention	1-1.75

Frequency and percentage were computed to classify respondents in terms of their demographic profile, while mean scores were computed to measure their perspectives toward hotel stay.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The demographic profile of the respondents was presented in the following section. Figure 3 shows that majority or 44% of the respondents are 18-27 years old, followed by those between 28-37 years old accounting to 32% of the population. Only 22% of the respondents are 38-47 years, while the least (2%) are those whose ages are between 48 and 57 years old during the conduct of the survey.

Several studies suggest younger generations are more engaged with tourism. The younger Gen Z's and Millennial are the highest spenders when they travel according an article by Condor Ferries on Travel Statistics by Age Group in 2020-2021, while in the report of the

United Nations World Tourism Organization (2016), it was explained that youth is one of the fastest growing segments in tourism accounting 23% of the over 1 billion international tourist arrivals in the past years globally.

Since there is a criteria set by the researchers on who are only qualified to participate in this study, one of which is to have an experience staying in a hotel in the last 5 years, this may indicate that most people engaged in tourism in the past five years from Calamba City are those who belong in the younger generations, confirming the claim of the aforementioned studies.

Figure 3: Respondents’ age distribution.

Figure 4 represents that most of the respondents are female (207 or 54%), while male are only 177 (46%). Based on the previous population census conducted by the Philippine Statistics Authority, there are more female than male in the Philippines but the gap is only roughly 1%. This explains the results of this study as the researchers randomly picked respondents guided by few criteria; if there are more female than male, then doing a random selection would more likely results in having more female than male respondents.

Figure 4: Respondents’ sex distribution.

Figure 5 indicates that most of the respondents are college graduates (229 or 60%), while 137 are secondary education graduates (36%). The rest are Master’s Degree graduates (12 or 3%), and primary education finishers who compose 1% (6) of the total respondents. Alejandria-Gonzalez (2016) has determined that majority of tourists in Palawan, Philippines are college graduates, therefore, showing that the case in Calamba City, Laguna is the same. Most hotel goers and travellers in the city are college graduates.

Figure 5: Respondents’ distribution by highest educational attainment.

Table 3 clearly shows that it is still not safe to stay in hotels even during this time that the country is recovering from the pandemic. Though there is no significant variance in the responses of the respondents, the lowest mean score was recorded at 1.96, stating that travelling and staying in hotels in the current times will still expose them to guests who are likely to be carriers/ infected of COVID-19, as well as to the risk of getting the virus from not sanitized or poorly sanitized beds, bed sheets, and other room fixtures used by guests. While the highest mean score (1.84) was recorded on the perspective of the respondents that staying in hotel will expose them to the risk of getting the virus from not sanitized or poorly sanitized eating utensils used by other guests.

Table 3: Respondents’ perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage in terms of safety and security.

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Meaning
I think that travelling and staying in hotels in the current times will still expose me to guests who are likely to be carriers/ infected of COVID-19	1.96	Agree
I think that travelling and staying in hotels in the current times will still expose me to the risk of getting the virus from not sanitized or poorly sanitized eating utensils used by guests	1.84	Agree
I think that travelling and staying in hotels in the current times will still expose me to the risk of getting the virus from not sanitized or poorly sanitized beds, bed sheets, and other room fixtures used by guests	1.96	Agree
I think that travelling and staying in hotels in the current times will still expose me to the risk of getting the virus from employees with poor hygiene that has direct contact with guests	1.86	Agree
I think that travelling and staying in hotels in the current times will still expose me to the risk of getting the virus and of failure in determining from whom/what I got it from	1.91	Agree

Table 4 stated that staying in a hotel is not ideal in terms of price. Though there is no significant gap in the responses of the respondents, the lowest mean score was recorded at 2.35, stating that hotels do not currently offer promotional rates for groups, while the highest mean score (1.82) is on the perception of respondents that travelling and staying in hotels in the current times is expensive. Therefore, the respondents believe that hotel rates are more

expensive and services do not promote group discounts and other forms of discounts in the current times compared to the pre-pandemic condition.

Table 4: Respondents' perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage in terms of price.

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Meaning
I think travelling and staying in hotels in the current times is expensive	1.82	Agree
I think that I could avail less services and products offered by hotels with the amount of money I normally spend, if I will travel and stay in hotels in the current times compared before	2.11	Agree
I think that travelling and staying in hotels in the current times would not give me access to discounts for services and products being offered	2.18	Agree
I think that hotels do not currently offer promotional rates for groups	2.35	Agree
I think that since only selected rooms are offered to guests, rates would be higher than before	1.89	Agree

Table 5 presents the respondents' perspective towards hotel stay in the current times in terms of location; it is clear that the respondents strongly agree that staying in a hotel located in a city/municipality that has high number COVID-19 cases is very dangerous with a mean score of 1.71, while they agree that hotels located in a city/municipality that has low number COVID-19 cases, those near and far from crowded places such as but not limited to airports and tourism destinations, and those located in secluded areas, could still expose them to the risk of getting the virus with mean scores of 2.05, 1.93, 2.11, 2.17 respectively. Therefore, wherever a hotel is located, in the opinion of the respondents, staying there is still risky since the country is still in a pandemic.

Table 5: Respondents' perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage in terms of location.

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Meaning
I think that staying in a hotel located in a city/municipality that has high number COVID-19 cases is very dangerous	1.71	Strongly Agree
I think that staying in a hotel located in a city/municipality that has low number COVID-19 cases is still risky since we are still in a pandemic	2.05	Agree
I think that staying in a hotel located near crowded places such as but not limited to airports and tourism destinations could still expose me to the risk of getting the virus	1.93	Agree
I think that hotels that are operational now are those located in selected areas only, limiting access to people who wants to travel	2.17	Agree
I think that staying in a hotel far away from crowded places (e.g. hotels in remote areas) could still expose me to the risk of getting the virus since we are still in a pandemic	2.11	Agree

Table 6 is a clear confirmation that in terms of service quality, the respondents’ perspective towards hotel stay in the current times is negative; they agree that the services offered by hotels are delivered slowly and inaccurately (2.30), lack of desirability (2.23), and cannot be personalized (2.28), in the current times compared before due to the risk of COVID-19. Additionally, they believe that hotels’ management cannot manage to control the spread of COVID-19 virus and that the utilization of amenities cannot be maximized the way it was being enjoyed before by guests due to strict health protocols implemented, with mean scores of 2.31 and 1.97 respectively.

Table 6: Respondents’ perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage in terms of service quality.

Statements	Mean	Descriptive Meaning
I think that the services offered by hotels in the current times are delivered slowly and inaccurately compared before	2.30	Agree
Hotels’ services in the current times lack of desirability due to the risk of COVID-19	2.23	Agree
I think hotels’ management cannot manage to control the spread of COVID-19 pandemic within their establishments in the current times	2.31	Agree
I think hotels in the current times cannot provide personalized services and respond immediately to concerns due to strict health protocols	2.28	Agree
I think hotels’ tangibles (facilities & amenities) utilization cannot be maximized the way it was being enjoyed before by guests due to strict health protocols implemented in the current times	1.97	Agree

Table 7 presents that people who belong in all age groups have a negative perspective towards hotel stay, however, in terms of safety and security, those who are 48-57 years old possess the least negative perception with a mean score of 2.27, while 18-27 years old perceive it most negatively. People who are 28-37 and 38-47 years old, on the other hand, thinks most positively in terms of price, while those who are between 48-57 years old perceive it most negatively. In terms of location, the highest mean score that is interpreted to be closest to being a positive perception belongs to those that are 38-47, and the least was recorded by people who are 18-27. Meanwhile, 28-37 years old perceived staying in hotels the most positively in terms of service quality, while the oldest age group, which is 48-57 thinks the most negatively.

Table 7: Respondents’ perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage in terms of each variable when grouped according to age.

Age Group	Safety and Security	Price	Location	Service Quality
18-27	1.81	2.07	1.92	2.20
28-37	1.89	2.08	1.98	2.28
38-47	1.94	2.08	2.05	2.18
48-57	2.27	2.04	2.02	2.07

Table 8 clearly shows that all age groups possess a negative perspective towards hotel stay in the current times, which consequently results to having a low stay intention. However, it is

noticeable that among all age groups, those that are 48-57 years old have the least negative perspective with a slight difference on their mean score, therefore, possess the highest chance of being convinced to stay in hotels through interventions, while the least mean score was recorded among those that are 18-27 years old, which translates to being the most difficult to convince.

Table 8: Respondents’ overall perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage when grouped according to age.

Age Group	Hotel Stay perspective (Overall Mean)	Perspective Interpretation	Hotel Stay Intention Interpretation
18-27	2.00	Negative	Low Stay Intention
28-37	2.06	Negative	Low Stay Intention
38-47	2.06	Negative	Low Stay Intention
48-57	2.10	Negative	Low Stay Intention

Table 9 presents that both female and male residents have a negative perspective towards hotel stay in terms of safety and security, price, location, and service quality. However, it is also noticeable that between the two, females have a more negative perspective in terms of safety and security, location, and service quality, while males possess a more negative perspective in terms of price with just a slight difference on mean scores.

Table 9: Respondents’ perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage in terms of each variable when grouped according to sex.

Sex Group	Safety and Security	Price	Location	Service Quality
Female	1.84	2.08	1.92	2.19
Male	1.92	2.07	2.03	2.26

Table 10 shows that both sex groups possess a negative perspective towards hotel stay in the current times, which consequently translates into a low stay intention. However, comparing the mean scores recorded in both, though there is slight difference; male residents have a more positive perspective, which means they are easier to be convinced that is now safe to stay in hotels.

Table 10: Respondents’ overall perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage when grouped according to sex.

Sex Group	Hotel Stay perspective (Overall Mean)	Perspective Interpretation	Hotel Stay Intention Interpretation
Female	2.01	Negative	Low Stay Intention
Male	2.07	Negative	Low Stay Intention

Table 11 presents that all groups except for those who have only finished primary education and lower possess a negative perspective towards hotel stay amidst the pandemic recovery stage in terms of safety and security, price, location, and service quality, while those primary education graduates and those who were not able finish primary education have negative perspective towards the said idea in terms of price, and a very negative perspective in terms of safety and security, location, and service quality.

Table 11: Respondents’ perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage in terms of each variable when grouped according to highest educational attainment.

Age Group	Safety and Security	Price	Location	Service Quality
Master’s Degree Graduate	2.03	2.05	2.00	2.55
College Graduate	1.91	2.07	1.99	2.25
Secondary Education Graduate	1.82	2.09	1.95	2.18
Primary Education Graduate	1.50	1.87	1.57	1.57

Table 12 shows that all groups in terms of highest educational attainment have a negative perspective towards hotel stay in the current times, which translates to having a low stay intention, while those who have only finished primary education or lower possess a very negative attitude towards staying in hotels, which translates to a very low stay intention. It is also noticeable that as the level of education gets higher, the mean scores gets higher, thus, the higher educational attainment a person has, the more positive his/her perspective is and the higher his/her stay intention becomes, which could also mean more educated people are more aware about the real situation of the hospitality industry amidst the pandemic recovery stage.

Table 12: Respondents’ overall perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage when grouped according to highest educational attainment.

Age Group	Hotel Stay perspective (Overall Mean)	Perspective Interpretation	Hotel Stay Intention Interpretation
Master’s Degree	2.16	Negative	Low Stay Intention
College	2.06	Negative	Low Stay Intention
Secondary Education	2.01	Negative	Low Stay Intention
Primary Education	1.63	Very Negative	Very Low Stay Intention

Table 13 shows that the respondents believe that it is not advisable to stay in hotels amidst the COVID-19 pandemic recovery stage; they clearly perceive the notion negatively in terms of safety and security, price, location, and service quality.

Table 13: Respondents’ perspective towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery stage in terms of each variable as a whole.

Variables	Mean Score	Descriptive Meaning	Perspective Interpretation
Safety and Security	1.90	Agree	Negative
Price	2.07	Agree	Negative
Location	1.99	Agree	Negative
Service Quality	2.22	Agree	Negative

Table 14 explains that as the hospitality industry tries to bounce back from the impact of the pandemic and the country attempts to open up the economy through businesses that are

back in operations; the public, particularly people of the City of Calamba, Laguna, Philippines are still not convinced that it is now advisable to stay in hotels with their perspective on it being negative with a mean score of 2.04, which translates to a hotel stay intention interpretation of Low Stay Intention.

Table 14: Respondents' overall perspective interpretation towards hotel stay amidst pandemic recovery as a whole.

Statement	Mean Score	Perspective Interpretation	Hotel Stay Intention Interpretation
Calamba City Residents' Perspective on Hotel Stay amidst pandemic recovery stage	2.04	Negative	Low Stay Intention

Results serve as indication that the Philippine tourism industry is likely to experience difficulty in fully recovering immediately as people still perceive travelling and staying in hotels negatively, as far the tourism market of the city of Calamba, Laguna is concern. This calls for actions from the government and industry managers, as well as the conduct of further studies covering a broader scope to understand the perspectives of other markets.

5. Conclusion, Implications and limitations

The researchers have found out that majority of those who have stayed in hotels in the past five years who live in Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines are between the ages of 18-37 years old since a significant criteria in the selection of respondents is experience of staying in a hotel at least once since 2017. These ages collectively falls under the age group called millennial. Prior the study, the researchers have already expected this because studies suggest that millennial composes a huge share in the tourism industry, in fact, Sofronov (2018) explains that millennial represents 27% of the global population or about 2 billion people, making it one of biggest tourism market. Moreover, these further justify the results since the researchers randomly picked respondents guided by few criteria; if there are more millennial engaged in tourism than other age groups, then doing a random selection would more likely results in having more millennial than other respondents who belong in different age groups.

It was also determined that there are more female tourists who have been staying in hotels in the past five years than males in the case of Calamba City, Philippines, with an 8% percentage gap. However, this could also mean that there are just more females than males in terms of the country's population, especially with the findings of the Philippine Statistics Authority in its recent census showing that there are more females than males in the Philippines, which means that doing a random selection would more likely result to having more female than male respondents. In terms of education attainment, the result shows that there are more respondents involved in the study that have finished college. This could be an indication that there are more college graduate travellers that have stayed in hotels in the past five years. The results of this study were also analyzed based on the people's demographic profile, and it indicated 48-57 years old have the least negative perspective on hotel stay with a slight difference on their mean score, while those that are 18-27 years old possess the most negative perception, leading to less hotel stay intention. In terms of sex, both males and females possess a negative perspective towards hotel stay in the current times, which consequently translates into a low stay intention as well, but males recording a slightly higher mean score create an impression that their perspective is a little less negative and their hotel stay intention is slightly higher amidst the pandemic recovery stage. Lastly, in terms of highest educational attainment, it was noticed that as the level of education gets higher, the mean scores get higher, thus, the higher educational attainment a person has, the more

positive his/her perspective is and the higher his/her stay intention becomes, which could also mean that educated people are more aware about the real situation of the hospitality industry amidst the pandemic recovery stage.

The people of Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines are generally not convinced that staying in hotels is now safe. They believe that traveling and staying in hotels will continue to expose them to guests who are likely to be COVID-19 carriers/infected; to the risk of getting the virus from not sanitized or poorly sanitized eating utensils used by guests; to the risk of getting the virus from not sanitized or poorly sanitized beds, bed sheets, and other room fixtures; to the risk of getting the virus from employees with poor hygiene who have direct contact with guests; and to the risk of getting the virus and of failure in determining from whom/what they got it from. Moreover, they believe that traveling and staying in hotels is currently expensive; that one could obtain fewer services and products offered by hotels with the amount of money normally spent compared to pre-pandemic times; that people will not have access to discounts and promotional rates for individuals and groups for the services and products being offered; and that rates will be higher than before because only selected rooms are offered to guests. In terms of location, respondents agreed that staying in a hotel located in a city/municipality with a high number of COVID-19 cases, as well as those located in a city/municipality with a low number of COVID-19 cases; those near and far from crowded places such as, but not limited to, airports and tourism destinations; and those located in secluded areas, is very dangerous due to the risk of contracting the virus. Furthermore, the local community of Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines considers that hotel services are delivered slowly and incorrectly; lack attractiveness; and cannot be personalized in the current times compared to previous times owing to the danger of COVID-19. Additionally, they claim that management of hotels are unable to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 virus and that the use of amenities cannot be maximized as to how it was previously enjoyed by visitors due to tight health regulations in place today.

The findings clearly indicates that the local community of Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines believes that it is not safe to stay in hotels nowadays, despite the attempt of the government to ensure public's safety and the notion of allowing hotels to accept guests as businesses try to bounce back from the losses incurred by the pandemic. It is clear that these people think that hotel rates are pricier and the quality of services is lower compared to the pre-pandemic times, that the management of hotels have poor protocols or standard operating procedures to prevent the spread of the virus within their premises and to conduct contact tracing, and that wherever hotels are located, it is still risky since the country is still in a pandemic. Therefore, currently possesses a low hotel stay intention, which could be an indicator that Filipinos are still hesitant to travel as they still perceive great treat from the pandemic. From the conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

- The millennial is a primary market in the tourism industry, hence, establishments such as hotels must focus on this generational group's demand as they show promising behavior that could help the industry recover from the pandemic.
- Hotels' Management must focus their marketing and promotional strategies in changing the perspective of the market towards travelling and staying in hotels, highlighting safety measures observed in the operations to ensure guests are safe from the virus such as but not limited to employees' hygiene, high number of vaccinated staffs, enforcement of social distancing, regular sanitation of amenities used by guests, and contact tracing protocols.
- Hotels' management is also recommended to include promotional offers, if there is any, on their advertisements, so that the market will be informed that the establishment is offering discounts for individuals, particularly returning guests, and incentives for guests who will check-in as a group. One suggestion is to consider a "Pandemic Recovery Promo" for those who will check-in until a specific timeframe. Additionally, it is important to establish a positive perceived value of hotels' services

among markets through influencers who could do vlogs that show the services being offered in the highest quality, television commercials, events, social media and email marketing, because this way, establishments would be able to convince people that the quality of services has been maintained despite strict health protocols that the management has to implement as they deliver services to guests.

- The government also plays a vital role in convincing the people that it is now safe to travel and stay in hotels, specially that the people involved in this study believe that location does not matter; as long as there is a pandemic, it is still unsafe to stay in any hotel no matter where it is located as they said. The government is hereby recommended to run information campaigns to let the public know that hotels that are operating have been assessed and is continuously being monitored to ensure that they follow protocols for the safety of guests.
- It is also recommended for the government to be vocal on the current situation of the country in terms of the pandemic, especially if the number of COVID-19 cases is decreasing. This would create an impression that the government is able to contain the virus and the country is recovering from the pandemic, hence, creating an impression that it is now safe to travel. Alongside with transparency, the government is also suggested to remove policies or at least be considerate on regulations that might make people think that the pandemic is still a great treat in the current times, such as but not limited to policy on face mask as a requirement in public spaces including malls, supermarket, government offices, schools, and parks. It is also a good initiative if the government would influence private companies to let their employees choose if they will wear mask or not at work, as this would establish a thought that COVID-19 is not a big deal anymore as measures have been put in place already.

The COVID-19 pandemic indeed had led to changes on people's attitude on tourism, making studies like this highly significant, however, this study has been conducted involving city residents only and has focused on just one city in the Philippines, hence, a study that evaluates the perspectives of rural communities and would cover a broader scope is recommended. Additionally, findings were limited to the perspectives of people towards staying in hotels in terms of safety and security, price, service quality, and location, which means this was not able to provide information about attitude on products and services offered by other sectors under the tourism industry; travel service, transportation, food and beverage, and recreation and entertainment, which is a research gap that future researchers could delved into.

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